

4th German Human Factors Summer
School

Program

Sept. 26.-27.th 2022

Organisators:

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Part I

General Information

Welcome

We are happy to welcome you all to the Fourth German Human Factors Summer School 2022. The German Summer School for Human Factors is the successor of the Berlin Summer School of Human Factors which was initiated and organized from 2014-2018 by the Department of Psychology and Ergonomics, TU Berlin. The Summer School is an annual postgraduate event that is supported by the Section of Engineering Psychology of the German Psychological Society (DGPs).

The intention is to provide an interactive platform that promotes the transfer and communication of interdisciplinary skills relevant to Human Factors research. Successful postgraduate applicants (Ph.D., M.Sc., and candidates) have the opportunity to present their research interests and/or current projects for critical discussion.

The 4th German Summer School for Human Factors is hosted by University of Mainz from September 26th to 27th. We are looking forward to inspiring talks and discussions.

Target audience

The target audience is Ph.D. students working in Human Factors, irrespective of whether they have just started or almost finished their Ph.D. The objective of the Summer School of Human Factors is to offer a space for Ph.D. students to connect and help each other with the empirical parts and handling of other issues concerning the Ph.D. Also, the summer school will be attended by invited senior researchers and guests, further facilitating the discussions.

Venue

The summer school will take place at the Department of Psychology (University of Mainz) located in Binger Straße 14-16, 55122 Mainz. The Department of Psychology can easily be reached by public transport or car.

- public transport – main station:
approx. 4 minutes walking distance

- car – Parkhaus Taubertsberg:
approx. 1 minute walking distance
- car – Parking lot at the main station (Alicenstraße P1 or Alicenstraße Brücke P2)
approx. 5 minutes walking distance

Accommodation

Check the connectivity between the venue and your preferred accommodation. We provide some suggestions for accommodation on our website.

Information for presenters

Each focus group will be scheduled for 5 + 45 minutes:

- Prior to the focus group (5 minutes), the presenters are kindly asked to give a sneak preview of their focus group (max. 40 seconds without slides).
- During the focus group (45 minutes), the contributor has the opportunity to initialize and lead a discussion about his/her current project. On this account, contributors can give a short introduction to their current project (max. 10 minutes) and use the rest of the time for an intense discussion with the audience. The room will be equipped with a laptop, a projector, a flip chart, etc.

We think the easiest way to conduct your session is that the audience will first listen to your short introductory talk (5-10 mins.). You can use the flip chart and/or some other form of presentation for your session. For the discussion, we provide notes, pens, etc. facilitating the creative process. We want to establish a convenient atmosphere for the speaker and a lively exchange of ideas later on.

Questions?

If you want to get in touch with the organizers to discuss some ideas or upcoming questions, please get in touch via email:

- sbranden@uni-mainz.de

Program

Monday, 26.09.2022

09:00 – 09:30 **Welcome JGU Mainz & FG-Ing.-Psy.**

Stefan Brandenburg and Martin Baumann

speed dating of the participants

Presentation – Discussion

Chair: Martin Baumann

09:30 – 10:20 Annika Schulz

10:25 – 11:15 Kim Klüber

11:15 – 12:05 Ksenia Appelganc

12:05 – 13:00 Lunch break

13:05 – 13:55 Liza Dixon

14:00 – 14:50 Sophie-Marie Stasch

14:55 – 15:45 Steffen Hoesterey

15:45 – 16:00 Coffee break

16:05 – 16:55 Markus Gödker

17:00 – 17:50 Elisabeth Wögerbauer

17:50 – 18:05 **End of the Day Summary (talking ball)**

18:05 – ... **Dinner**

Tuesday, 27.09.2022

09:00 – 09:10 Welcome day two

09:15 – 10:00 Journal Compass: reaching suitable target groups with your research
Martin Baumann, Stefan Brandenburg

Presentations – Discussions

Chair: Martin Baumann

10:15 – 11:25 Michèle Rieth

11:30 – 12:20 Laura Prislán

12:30 – 13:20 Norman Riedel

13:20 – 13:40 **End of the Summer School Summary**

13:40 – 14:30 **Lunch Break and taking farewell**

Presentation topics

Annika Schulz	Robert Bosch GmbH	Designing Tangible Interfaces for Shared Smart Homes
Kim Klüber	HU Berlin	Affect-enhancing Speech Characteristics for Robotic Communication
Ksenia Appalganc	Universität Bremen	Human-agent teaming in a Mars habitat: The effect of linguistic framing on trust and performance
Liza Dixon	Robert Bosch GmbH	Control Management: Human-Machine Interaction Design and the Paradigm Shift of High Driving Automation
Sophie-Marie Stasch	Universität der Bundeswehr München	The role of cognitive control states in the relationship between multitasking and the stability-flexibility dilemma in flight missions
Steffen Hoesterey	HU Berlin	Measurement of operator's perception of role and accountability
Markus Gödker	Universität Lübeck	Effects of Energy Interfaces on Energy Dynamics Awareness and EcoDriving Optimization
Elisabeth Wögerbauer	JGU Mainz	Implications of camera-monitor-systems for rearward perception in an automotive environment
Michèle Rieth	Universität Bremen	Adaptable Automation for a more human-centered work design in High Reliability Organizations?
Laura Prislán	Robert Bosch GmbH	Fostering sustainable behavior in consumer clusters
Norman Riedel	KIT Karlsruhe	Cognitive-Motor-Interference in Human-Exoskeleton-Interaction

Part II

Abstracts

Designing Tangible Interfaces for Shared Smart Homes

Annika Sabrina Schulz

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The most predominant interfaces to control smart home technology include smartphones and speech interfaces. However, both modalities impact social life at home from a socio-technical perspective, shaping relationships between people who live together. Interactions with smart homes reinforce, among others, gender roles in the home. Besides, interacting with smart home networks using the current devices creates a high cognitive load. We aim to design future interfaces that blend better with the nature of homes. In previously conducted co-creation sessions, we explored the expectations of future smart home interfaces from analog-looking materials. We discovered that users require highly flexible systems covering homely and functional perspectives. On the one side, this includes offering a shelter in which humans find rest and perform leisure activities. On the other hand, household chores are performed at home, requiring communication and coordination between the members of a shared household. Besides, it must adapt to different contexts and user preferences in individual and social settings. Approaching the topic from a feminist perspective, we aim to design smart home interfaces accessible for all users in shared households, acknowledging their individual preferences and needs and encourage users to communicate, care for each other and distribute chores more equally. To achieve familiarity and good user experience with the future device, we borrow characteristics from books representing an artifact located in many different contexts at home used by several persons. Right now, we are conducting semi-structured interviews with book experts to understand analog books' characteristics better. Analyzing the qualitative data in thematic analysis, we want to discover tangible elements, concepts, and metaphors to transfer to interaction with smart home networks. Content-wise, we want to

enable users to perform similar activities in their smart homes as with analog books: immersing in other worlds, creating, and reflecting on habits or routines, planning, and engaging in communicating and sharing with others, overall focusing on decelerating aspects to foster users' wellbeing at home. Together with prospective users' we plan to create initial prototypes relying on tangible and blended interaction as paradigms using results from the book study as a toolkit. To underline the analog look and feel of interfaces blending with the home's interior, we plan to investigate usability and user experience with prototypes from smart materials (e.g., textiles, printed electronics). In the focus group, I would like to discuss preliminary results regarding the characteristics of analog books that we would like to depict in the prospective device and explore suitable use cases to represent in the prototype.

Affect-enhancing Speech Characteristics for Robotic Communication

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As robots increasingly adopt human-like appearances and manners, people tend to treat robots like social actors and ascribe minds to those non-human entities (Duffy, 2003; K. Gray & Wegner, 2012). According to the theory of mind, mind in other agents is perceived on two dimensions (H. M. Gray et al., 2007): the experience dimension describes the attribution of feelings and vulnerability, the agency dimension refers to the attribution of the ability to think, to intentionally act, and to be responsible. The perception of experience and agency determines how robots are treated - with higher experience leading to more sympathy and forgiveness with robots (Yam et al., 2021). One strategy to increase the experience ratings of robots while not increasing agency is the application of affective communication (Taylor, 2009). When considering speech as communication channel, two components can be distinguished that convey emotions. The verbal component includes the word level and determines the lexical features. The prosodic component includes the variation in intonations (e.g., pitch, timing, loudness) and determines the acoustic features (James et al., 2020).

I have already conducted two online studies to investigate the influence of verbal component and prosody on the experience and agency dimension. In the online studies, participants listened to audios in which robots introduced themselves. In study I, the audios differed on the verbal content with regard to *emotional* words, *subjective* narration (within factors), and *prosodic* speech (between factor). In study II, the audios differed in regard to *emotional* words and *prosody* (within factor) while an additional *robot picture* was presented during the audios (between factor). Overall, we found that the use of emotional words and prosodic speech increased the experience dimension, whereas

agency was not affected. However, the positive effect of prosody was dependent on the presented robot. Speaking in a more subjective way had no impact on the investigated factors.

To investigate the observed effects in an actual interaction and with an embodied robot, I am currently planning a laboratory experiment. The aim is to go beyond the solely perception of experience and focus on the impact of an increased experience component with regard to trust and forgiveness. Since these variables are strongly dependent on a real interaction, trust and forgiveness shall play a crucial role in the following experiment. It is planned to perform the experiment with Nao and to complete three tasks. Task 1 (a **question-answer task**) aims to interact with the robot and thereby introduce the manipulation on affective speech. The second task (**balloon analogue risk task**) aims to measure trust. In the third task (a **teaching task with a failure experience**), participants would first teach something to the robot (e.g., rock-paper-scissors) and afterwards test it. During the test phase, the robot makes a failure. After this, participants have the opportunity to teach the robot again or to continue with the experiment. It is assumed that the more often participants repeat the teachings, the more forgiving they are. In the focus group, I would like to exchange views on the proposed experiment, but also more generally with regard to objective measures on trust and forgiveness in HRI.

References

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- Gray, H. M., Gray, K., & Wegner, D. M. (2007). Dimensions of mind perception. *science*, 315(5812), 619–619.
- Gray, K., & Wegner, D. M. (2012). Feeling robots and human zombies: Mind perception and the uncanny valley. *Cognition*, 125(1), 125–130.
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Yam, K. C., Bigman, Y. E., Tang, P. M., Ilies, R., De Cremer, D., Soh, H., & Gray, K. (2021). Robots at work: People prefer- and forgive - service robots with perceived feelings. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 106*(10), 1557.

Human-agent teaming in a Mars habitat: The effect of linguistic framing on trust and performance

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Exploring other planets like Mars will pose immense challenges for humans. One of the many reasons is the deadly environment on the planet. Therefore, the crew will have to live in a habitat that ensures their survival with the help of a life support system (LSS). In our project “The Living Habitat“ we aim to integrate a photobioreactor (PBR) into the MaMBA habitat laboratory at the Center of Applied Space Technology and Microgravity (ZARM) at the University of Bremen as a component of a LSS. The PBR should revitalize the air with the help of cyanobacteria and adapt to the changing oxygen requirements of the crew. In order for the crew to monitor the PBR, we plan to develop situationally aware and interactive sensor networks. Since the crew could not survive without the LSS it is of utmost importance that the crew can trust the system and rely on it. Furthermore, the LSS needs to function as autonomously as possible because the crew has to work on numerous tasks and doesn't have the capacity to constantly monitor the LSS. One could argue that such an autonomous technical system could even be considered as a further team member within a human-agent team. In our first experiment we aim to investigate the effect of linguistic framing of such an artificial agent as a tool or a team member. The experiment will take place in the Mars habitat at ZARM. Participants will work together as a team of two (one participant and one agent) with an artificial agent. After a short familiarization phase their task will be to repair the life support system with verbal instruction from the agent. We will follow the Wizard of Oz paradigm to simulate the agent. Participants will have to verbally interact with the agent in order to solve the

task. This agent will be introduced as a team member or a tool prior to the interaction through a written description. We want to analyze how such a framing influences trust in the agent and the effect it has on the performance. Furthermore, we want to explore the communication between the participant and the agent. At the Summer School for Human Factors, I would like to present the initial idea of our experimental design and discuss this design and especially the dependent variables.

Effects of Energy Interfaces on Energy Dynamics Awareness and EcoDriving Optimization

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Energy-efficient driving (ecodriving) in electric vehicles is a crucial skill to reduce range stress and to enhance the ecological footprint of electric vehicles. Yet, due to the invisibility of energy itself and the high volatility of the energy transformations, it is very demanding for drivers of electric vehicles to judge which situations or actions are energy efficient and to decide on efficient actions. Energy interfaces support the accurate perception and understanding of energy consumption and are often a built-in feature in electric vehicles. Yet, it is unclear how energy feedback displays can optimally support drivers in their eco-driving. In this presentation, I give an overview of a theoretical framework draft that describes how energy related information is processed to drive more energy-efficiently. I assume that in accordance with situation awareness literature, an accurate situation awareness of the energy dynamics (i.e., energy dynamics awareness, EDA) can enable energy-efficient decisions and actions and, hence, eco-driving improvement. Based on this framework, we designed a driving simulator study with two different instantaneous consumption displays that are assumed to support eco-driving to different degrees due to the information they depict. In this design, the participants drive the same route eight times and have the task to reduce the energy consumption on this route with the help of instantaneous consumption displays while reaching the goal in time. We measure the average consumption each trial to observe how the participants improve their eco-driving. Several additional measures are repeatedly collected to estimate energy-related information processing and energy dynamics awareness throughout the trials. To check for display-related

differences, the participants are divided into three groups (display A, display B, no display). I present preliminary results of the pilot data collection and discuss the theoretical framework as well as the design of the experiment.

Implications of camera-monitor-systems for rearward perception in an automotive environment

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The use of conventional rear-view mirrors is very familiar to drivers, but increasingly these rear-view mirrors are being replaced by camera-monitor-systems (CMS). In these systems, a camera is placed instead of the side-mounted rear-view mirror, sending the recordings to a monitor display in the vehicle. In addition to improved aerodynamics, CMS offer a variety of possibilities to enhance the image in order to improve rearward perception and, as a result, road safety. However, the decoupling of the rearward viewing axis from the driver's viewing axis could raise problems.

So far, research has focused on the placement of the in-vehicle monitor and its effects on driving performance, hazard detection and gaze behaviour. Only little attention has been dedicated to the placement of the camera. Based on experiments by Bernhard and Hecht (Bernhard & Hecht, 2021) on the vertical camera placement with regard to distance estimation, we want to investigate the effect of the horizontal placement of the camera.

Based on the outcome of this investigation, we want to explore the interaction of camera and monitor placement and work out whether previous findings on the placement of the in-vehicle monitor can also be found for other than the conventional mirror position. As a result, requirements for the design of CMS could be developed. Furthermore, we are interested in the opportunities that CMS offer to implicitly enhance the displayed image. How can rearward perception be improved and, for example, the identification of dangerous situations be supported by a CMS? Depending on whether only rearward perception or also driving behaviour is being investigated, the experiments will

be conducted in a screen-based setting or in a virtual reality driving simulation. We are interested in how behavioural, subjective and psychophysiological parameters are affected in different configurations of CMS.

The first two planned experiments use a prediction-motion paradigm in which the first-person vehicle does not move and another vehicle approaches from behind in the mirror/monitor. This vehicle becomes invisible at specified times and the subject's task is to estimate the time it would take this vehicle to reach his/her own position from that moment. One experiment intends to find out whether already known effects on time-to-contact estimation can also be found when the camera position is displaced horizontally. The other experiment investigates how a simplification of the displayed image (by removing task-irrelevant cues such as texture and environmental information) affects time-to-contact estimation.

I would like to present the planned design of these two experiments and discuss in the focus group what needs to be considered when collecting the dependent variables.

References

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Control Management: Human-Machine Interaction Design and the Paradigm Shift of High Driving Automation

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The deployment of highly automated vehicles capable of operating in multiple driving modes and levels of automation (SAE Level 4 dual-mode vehicles) will mark a significant technological achievement. In addition, these vehicles represent a paradigm shift for human-machine interaction (HMI) in driving automation due to their potential ability to conditionally reallocate control, authority, and responsibility, resulting in behaviors such as a “delayed user-requested disengagement“ (SAE J3016). We refer to this advanced system property as Control Management in automated driving.

Highly authoritative Control Management behaviors such as Automation Gatekeeping (the automation withholding control from the driver) and Automation Seeking (the automation overtaking control from the driver) are foreseeable consequences of the continued development of driving automation. These behaviors are likely to present significant challenges for the cooperating human driver which may lead to existential crises, both for the technology itself via potential disuse and for human autonomy in automated driving. Therefore, we need to examine drivers’ willingness to cooperate with systems capable of Control Management and, through the manipulation of the HMI design, determine if conflicts can be mitigated and collaborative control and safety can be supported.

Two simulator studies are planned to investigate HMI design concepts for conflict mitigation in instances of Control Management. The initial simulator

study focuses on steering wheel haptics, during which participants will experience different haptic designs in a series of randomized scenarios designed to maximize conflict between the driver's intention and the intention of the automated system. In two of the scenarios, the automation withholds manual control from the driver (Automation Gatekeeping) and, in two other scenarios, the automation overtakes control from the driver (Automation Seeking). The haptic designs will be evaluated by the participants via objective (e.g., control(s) input, gaze) and subjective measures (e.g., questionnaires) for their controllability, comfort, and trustworthiness. Participants' attitudes towards and the acceptance of Control Management will also be examined.

By defining and identifying critical conflicts in driving automation we might support measuring and predicting their occurrence. In doing so, we can work to reduce instances of conflict and support human autonomy in automated driving. The focus group discussion will center on two points: 1) the theoretical background on how we communicate these new HMI design challenges, and 2) the variables to be manipulated in future simulator studies. This work represents a step forward in addressing a contentious aspect of safety-critical automation by provoking research questions, developing HMI design solutions, and emphasizing the importance of human-centered automation.

The role of cognitive control states in the relationship between multitasking and the stability-flexibility dilemma in flight missions

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Flight missions are highly complex multitasking scenarios. They require concurrent and sequential multitasking behaviour while performing two or more flight tasks at the same time, i.e., aviate, navigate and communicate. The following PhD-project aims at investigating the strategic use of cognitive flexibility, meaning the adaptation of action in response to situational changes, on multitasking behaviour during these flight missions. Cognitive flexibility, as part of executive functions, is subject to the stability-flexibility dilemma. This dilemma is associated with several advantages and disadvantages: On the one hand, cognitive stability has the advantage of maintaining goals and shielding them from distractors. On the other hand, cognitive stability is associated with reduced background monitoring and perseveration. In contrast, cognitive flexibility has the advantage of enabling flexible task switching and the rapid detection of potentially significant incidents. However, a distinct disadvantage of cognitive flexibility is impulsiveness and the interference by distractors.

It is yet unknown how the stability-flexibility dilemma relates to multitasking behaviour in flight missions. It is hypothesized that a stable cognitive control state relates to serial task performance and supports focused decision-making by avoiding distraction from irrelevant task demands. Contrary, a flexible control state is predicted to relate to parallel task performance. This control state should enhance time efficiency and reactivity to unpredictable

changes as well as task-switching.

To investigate this, the project aims at identifying instances in which a flexible or stable control mode is strategically beneficial for the current mission tasks and objectives. Secondly, it is of particular interest which behavioural and eye-tracking metrics are suitable for diagnosing the cognitive control mode in real time. By identifying measurable correlates of the control mode, an adaptive cognitive assistance system can take these correlates into account for the user state diagnosis. With successful detection of the control state employed by the pilot, an automated cockpit could compensate for the associated disadvantages of either control mode.

It is planned to combine qualitative data collected by semi-structured interviews in the real flight simulator with quantitative data from a controlled laboratory environment. In order to investigate the cognitive control state in a laboratory environment, a suitable method for manipulating it must initially be developed. To this end, an initial pilot study has already been conducted with the Multi-Attribute Task Battery (MATB). The MATB is a flight-like experimental environment and simulates four flight tasks that also occur in a similar form in real flight missions. A feedback score, calculated based on the distribution of fixations, and an instruction were used to manipulate the cognitive control mode. Two conditions were induced: a stable and flexible control state. In addition to demographics and performance data, eye movements were recorded. A follow-up study is planned that will base the calculation of the feedback score on immediate performance.

During the focus group, it will be discussed which correlates, i.e., behavioural and physiological, are appropriate to detect the cognitive control state in flight missions. Preliminary results of the pilot study will be discussed at the end of the focus group.

Measurement of operator's perception of role and accountability in interaction with automation support

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A key goal when implementing new automation is that operators appropriately trust it. A lot of research has been conducted to understand effects of automation's system characteristics on attitudinal and behavioral operator trust. The relationship of these two constructs is one of the main topics of my dissertation. The results of a recent laboratory experiment of ours showed that participants working with an automated aid with a higher degree of automation (decision automation) initially had a lower trust attitude than participants with a lower degree of automation (information automation). This was not expected as both aids were equally reliable and non-transparent. Only after a longer interaction experience with their aids, both groups reported a similar high trust attitude. In an attempt to explain this initial group difference after a very short interaction experience, we hypothesized that participants had different perceptions of the purpose of their respective aids as well as different role and accountability perceptions. When the decision-making process is automated the role of the operator can be described as supervisory. In this case one could argue that it is the operator's main task to inherently challenge/distrust their automation. In contrast, if only information analysis is automated and the aid merely points in the direction of the correct diagnosis, but the decision must still be made by the operator, the purpose of the automation might be perceived differently: as a helpful tool with which trust, or distrust simply does not play as an important role. The main question which I would like to discuss has been on my mind for a long time: What are ways to measure operator's perception of role and accountability of themselves and of

the automated aid? So far, in a separate laboratory experiment we have tried a quantitative and a qualitative approach and both were not to our satisfaction: First, we used straight forward self-made single items asking about their perception of their role and accountability. Second, we tried to extract these perceptions from post-hoc interviews we conducted with the participants after the experiments. However, probably due to a lack of experience in qualitative research and possibly not ideal questions, these interviews were not very useful to us. During my focus group I would mainly like to collect and discuss ideas to measure these concepts (quantitatively or qualitatively) including a new quantitative approach that I have not tried out yet.

Adaptable Automation for a more human-centered work design in High Reliability Organizations?

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Within the scope of my PhD project I am analyzing the effects of increasing automation on employees in High Reliability Organizations using the example of Air Traffic Controllers. Thereby, the focus is on the realization of a human-centered design following the concept of a Joint Cognitive System. Our previous studies indicate that the experience of competence and autonomy is particularly important to this group of employees, but that these are increasingly reduced by higher degrees of automation. Adaptable automation (AA) represents a promising approach to utilize the advantages of conventional automation approaches and at the same time counteract those unintended consequences that are associated with static automation concepts (e.g. loss of perceived autonomy and competence). The latter seem to be most likely when automation crosses a critical boundary from information automation (IA) to decision automation (DA). In an experimental online study, we systematically examine the mostly theoretically postulated advantages of AA compared to static automation. We hypothesized that perceived competence and autonomy is significantly higher under AA and static IA than under static DA, that satisfaction with the automation support is significantly higher under AA than under IA and DA, and that there are significant differences in the role perception between the groups. Participants had to manage an artificial dynamic traffic scenario by controlling intersections with automation support in a dual-task paradigm. We use three different conditions, in which one of the three assistance systems is applied: IA, DA, or an adaptable solution in which participants can switch between the two types of automation. Participants had to perform five trials: The first trial was a manual one; trial 2 to 4

were with automation support and the last trial was manual again. The study was conducted with two samples: A sample of novices (via the crowdsourcing platform Prolific; $N = 93$) and a sample of experts (Air Traffic Controllers; $N = 126$). The results confirmed in both samples that adaptable automation is a suitable approach to counteract some negative consequences associated with increasing automation in static automation concepts. It can increase the experience of autonomy, leads to a high level of satisfaction, and in some cases has a positive effect on role perception without leading to significant performance losses or workload increases. However, no effect on perceived competence was found and there were some minor differences between novices and experts. Participation in the Summer School for Human Factors would be the optimal opportunity to discuss these results, especially in comparison of the two samples, and to discuss a suitable publication strategy for this planned paper with both samples.

Fostering sustainable behavior in consumer clusters

Laura Prislán

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There is a big discrepancy between the planned actions of people to reduce their CO₂-footprint and the actual CO₂ reduction of these actions. People are not aware of energy saving potential in consumer technology, for example in their washing machines. Adapted design has the potential to promote sustainable behavior. An initial literature review on factors influencing sustainable behavior was conducted. It became clear that the initial situation of the user is not yet sufficiently understood in the context of consumer technology. A better problem description is needed. To build up this understanding on a solid basis, semi-structured user interviews were conducted. Five different sustainability types emerged in the study. The types differ in several categories such as their goals and intentions towards sustainable behavior, reflection upon their own behavior, values and more. An important point is that different types can be motivated to different degrees by different measures. A currently running online-study based on a quantitative questionnaire is conducted to validate these types. It measures e.g., self-reported factors like consciousness for sustainable consumption, knowledge of pro-environmental products, perceived consumer effectiveness, environmental concern, social norms, values, and skepticism. According to the preregistration the dependent variable for clustering is consciousness for sustainable consumption, other variables will be exploratively examined. Feature selection or feature extraction shall help to identify the relevant features as basis for the next study. The main limitation is that this does not measure real behavior so far. This point will be addressed in the follow-up study in a behavioral study. If the two validation studies are successful, another follow-up study will develop and test communication strategies for the different clusters. In the discussion slot, it would be desirable to discuss especially the structure of the behavioral experiment. As a suggestion, two possibilities will be presented at the end of the 10-minute talk.

Cognitive-Motor-Interference in Human-Exoskeleton-Interaction

Norman Riedel

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Body-worn assistance systems or exoskeletons are already being used in some domains such as rehabilitation and industry. Such systems are intended to increase, support or even enable the physical performance of the user, depending on the respective objective. For elderly people, for example, exoskeletons can create more autonomy and independence in everyday life, enabling them to live in their own homes. Exoskeletons for everyday use have not yet become established, which is due not only to the technical limitations but also to the complex requirements of everyday movements. In addition to physical support, it is essential that wearing or controlling exoskeletons does not cause increased cognitive demands in the user. Especially in the early interaction phase, an increased demand could lead to the technology not being accepted and no long-term and regular use being desired. Especially if the target group is seniors, increased cognitive load can lead to an increased risk of falls and impaired cognition in multi-task situations (Priest et al., 2008). In this context, the research group around Leia Stirling established the term *cognitive fit* of exoskeletons (Stirling et al., 2020). In a field study, they were able to show that wearing a lower extremity exoskeleton can lead to reduced reaction times in a visual search task (Bequette et al., 2020).

In this research field, I would like to start with my PhD project. I am investigating the extent to which altered leg mechanics (weights attached to the legs or active/passive exoskeletons for lower extremities) influence gait pattern, cognitive demands, and subjectively perceived workload. The focus of this research is on cognitive-motor interference during walking with and without an exoskeleton. As a starting point, I am currently planning an initial